

CREATING AND INNOVATIVE ELEMENTS OF SCIENCE IN THE WORKS OF NAVOI

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Abstract: This article in the works of A. Navoi deals with the innovative fields of science.

Key words: works, scientific works, works of art, creating of science, innovative elements, a magic mirror.

We must pay special attention to the fact that the invaluable legacy of our great masters of artistic forces, our saints, invincible commanders and heroes penetrate the consciousness of young people, strengthen the feeling of national pride and joy in them. (1)

Nizomiddin Mir Alisher Navoi is a master of artistic power, who in the history of worldview, thinking with his works of art destroyed the world. If the descendants of the great master are left to inherit more than twenty volumes, then the theme is wide, diverse. His works do not attach any importance today. His scientific works were written by the poet as works of fiction, also serve as a source for modern science. These works contain rich materials related to the language, literature, history of Turkic people. For example, in the essay "Debatamat-ul lugatayn" he compares the Persian language and reveals the meaning of the Turkic language with the proofs (2). During the period when the ruler of Huarosan, Boycott, issues a law on the Turkic language, in response to this law, Navoi wrote "Hamsa" in Turkish and made a decisive contribution to the preservation and increase of the authority of our language. The work "Mezon ul-avzon" is for in literary science in the Turkic language. If panic arises before A. Navoi, he will bring this to six years. In this work, he proves and explains his position. In historiography, A. Navoi created the works "Tarihi anbiyo and hukamo" and "The History of Muluki Ajam." In his works, he details the history of prophet and death, the names of the sixty-three kings who ruled in Turan and Iran, their translational state, and the policies pursued (3). Let's see which of the works of A. Navoi is reflected by the artistic plan of the poet. His works include peace, the well-being of the country, a just king, as well as the power of creating science. For example, in "Khairat-ul-Abror" it was evaluated by science.

When the scientist is forgotten and ugly, the Bogatik pecks at the silent bone on the stone of the Kashshak child, he has the intention that I will be able to know, he does not let him down from the hand of Kitob, he says that I will go to the top of Bilyk. He occupied a sea of knowledge and he loved him, - (4) We great science. We can see such idea in all the works of Navoi.

In "Leili Majnun," Kais and Leili are also in the lower grades. At school, Kais reveals rapid literacy, acquires all knowledge, surprises teachers, peers. At this place, Navoi Olla wants to show his special talent to his favorite gangs (5) (Navoishunask, Tamaddun-Tashkent, 2019,123 b)

In the world of "Farhod and Shirin," science great at a high level. At this point, Navoi's goals and ideas are also evident. The son of the Shah of the country Farhad Qin, with appearing and good qualities, surprises others.

U'n yoshlaridayoq,

Jahonda qolmadi u etmagan ilm,

Bilib anglamagan, egallamagan ilm,- Will reach the level.

In the work, Farhad is portrayed as a person of physically powerful, boundless talent with high qualities. After he has mastered all the sciences of the world, he will not be left with anything interesting, so Farhad will get sick. Since she was only child, her parents always took care of her. He builds the palace according to the beginning of the year in order to gain the strength of his child and develop the mood.

During the construction of this palace, Farhad acquires the profession of stone craft, painting and memorial. During the execution of these crafts, a sharp aggravation occurs. Parents were very strong in this work of their child. After Farhad falls ill again, his father eventually offers him the throne. At the same time, he wanted to find a cure for his child, but Farhad, doing work to manage the country, gave him permission to gain experience. After that, he begins to get acquainted with his father's countless wealth in the state room. Here he is interested in the laconic window in the chest, which is stored in the room behind the parda. Farhad receives permission from his parents to reveal the mystery of the window. To solve this secret, you need to get rid of the risks. Parents do not want to send it, since they have only child. A. Navoi reads that through this it is difficult to master the purulent science, that in this country there should be no tarnished exercises so that a person does not kneel. The mood of the parents, who felt that the child's condition was beginning to deteriorate, does not subside, and eventually allows the secret of the magic window to leave. His father gives him a strong army. To reveal the mystery of the window with this army. To reveal the secrets of science, it is necessary, first of all, to teach yourself, to become a mentor. His mentors Suhaylo, Sukrat helps him. Suhaylo reports on the need to overcome the dragon, maiden, iron to reveal the mystery and provides to overcome the dragon. If this is sucked to the body, then he survives the death of the dragon. Having overcome all the feathers, he heads for Sucrot. When I talk to Sukrat Farkhod: - Kid, Farhad, I've been waiting for you for eight hundred years. Nature has always hidden all the secrets of humanity. Only you discover this mystery, "she says and gives the key to the magic window and admires the world. After laborious work, Farhad removes the knot of science and reveals the secret of the window. Thanks to this, Navoi also advocates the artistic intention of thoughts about science and the secrets of the world, so that humanity owns science and discovers the secrets of the world. The greating of the poet of science when writing the name of Greek philosophers is obvious here. Revealed the secret of this magical window, in which the daughter of Guzal from Armenia Shirin. Thanks to this, the poet for centuries tried to embody in his works arman, interests, innovative minds of our people, to demonstrate the interest of mankind in revealing world secrets, there by describing the artistic intentions of his people. Now I have solved the mystery and Farhad cannot be seen. He wanted to go to Armenia and burn Shirin because he fell in love with this girl. But parents don't want to send him for being a only child. Farhad cannot realize his goal. He called all famous doctors. They advise living in humid air when water has decreased on the child's body. Farhad's parents send Farhad to live on the island at sea with all his people. A strong hurricane broke out in the sea, whose people, swimming in the sea, surviving Farhad and find

traders selling the sea. Due to the fact that they learned the skills of shooting with a pistol and grenade, the merchants receive savings from the robbers. The traders agree and deliver Farhad to the address. Here the poet asked ideas young man seven crafts: "You are thinking." After much training, Farhad rejoiced to celebrate the Width (6). At the time, the country of Breadth was suffering from dehydration. In this country, Farhad uses stone crafts, through delivering water to the people and saves them from dehydration. Together with science, he reads that artisans are leading in communication that a person should serve in the interests of the country. The poet "Saddi Iskandari" also has a desire for science, the power of greating science. The main image in this world is Iskandar Zulkarnein. His father is already paying attention to the upbringing of everyone tomorrow. Father Arasto gives his hands to Naukmo-body for training, and the child becomes the same as his father. Alexander is interested in science of moral qualities.

Alexander was to inherit the throne. Residents are firmly demanding shock from him, but Iskandar is in no hurry. He advises his mentors, relies, after which his mentor Arasta puts a crown on him. Iskander sets conditions for the people, and who has claims, makes the horn equal to himself and makes them talk about the state of affairs. After Alexander ascends the throne, he begins to rule the country fairly. Shoch has deep knowledge, thanks to his moral qualities, he begins primarily with the developing of the situation of the people. Because he spoke to Arasta's mentor about justice. The poet explains justice with stories.

For example, when Shah Masood once exclaimed about how his father Mahmood walked paradise, how you and your father handled this situation, he says that because of the justice he worked for the country during the conquest of India, Olla deserved it. In the life of Alisher Navoi - robberies for tax, due to injustice there is a lot of instability in the country. The poet dreamed of fair rock, which caused harm to the people, the negative influence of these caring people. If the poet works in every work on the basis of the heart of justice, his country will prosper, his people will be rich and the wages of soldiers will grow, the army will always achieve through the image of Arasta works were amateur performances of the poet, his goals and intentions. Alexander Zulkarnein's "Saddy Iskandari" is portrayed as a just shah.

His fame became famous after the victory of the Iranian Shah in the war with Dara. Impostors betray the tree and stab it. Alexander finds Dara wounded. Before his death, Dara sets three conditions, obliges him to punish traitors, not feed enemies and marry Ravshnak's daughter. He buries the tree ethically, fulfills all his wills on his own. A. Navoi says that Iskandar is an unlimited decent lover, along with the world-famous shakh. He spared no help if small layers suffered from large beds.

This allowed them to live well and peacefully. Therefore, Iskander became famous for his honesty and nobility at a high level. After Alexander the Tsar has taken possession of all the land, he proceeds to flood the sea. Having made dishes from Shiisha, he lived a life under the sea for 12 years. This place also talks about science. The desire of Shakh, occupying all land, and the desire for the sea, and the interest in this science, in revealing the secrets of the world, are born events from the innovative branches of the poet. Navoi expresses innovative views through the image of Iskandar. Shakh's conversation with his mother after his death, that is, about peace, is also a secret peace from humanity. Due to the fact that Navoi was interested in the secret of the world (7).

A big place in the partnership of A. Navoi is occupied by the theme of nobility. He attached great importance to the topic of nobility in all world literature, demanded a high level of nobility in any person (8).

Meni ishq darli emas, yurt darti qiynar,
Boshimdan ketmaydi ming turli u'ylar
Odam deb atama unday odamni,
Xalq gamini u'ylamagan yomonni

We feel that the poet has always lived in his hands, taking care of the peace, well-being and justice of the country. This was due to the fact that Hussein took Baikara the throne of Huroson. Invites Navoi to the Palace to work, goes from Deputy Prime Minister to Prime Minister. During this period Herat became a thriving center of science. Because with Shakh, the minister has always supported each other in matters of education, literature, governance of the country, justice. The reason for the developing of the country was that the Shakh and the minister turned into the center of science, which flourished from a ruthless. Students in madrasas have always supported. Those who has worked well recently were awarded a scholarship at a lower level. Despite the fact that there was such a difficult time during this period, we see that science is supported, as it is today. I am grateful for scientists and prophets of these works. We can see that the poet shows interest in greating these thoughts, revealing and knowing the secrets of the world. In his works, he described in detail and handed them over to the people. He considered peace, justice, science to be basis for the developing of the country. The point is that the works of A. Navoi have grown for centuries and have survived to this day

In fact, in combination with today's policy, Uzbekistan is harmony, human dignity, human greating, the peace of the country, justice, comprehensive support for young people, ensuring the well-being of the country. In this regard, the President of our country Sh.M. Mirziyoyev said: "Literature is the heart of the people, symbolizes the spiritual world of the country, in today's difficult, difficult time we must use the effective power of literature to attract people to good work, inspiration (9) in a state of alcoholic intoxication.

«Turkiy tilda qu'lga olib qalamni,
Qalam bilan bu'ysundirdim olamni»

- great thinker who has scientifically high quality of advantages of Turkic language, not indifferent poet of national culture Navoi, promotes young people to achieve community, high level of humanism, patriotism, innovative development.

When we hand young people the works of each master of art, we must deeply educate in their hearts about personalities who can awakes the feelings of the homeland, human dignity, high nobility, science great feelings. Only then can we create a fair, innovative, democratic civil society.

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